

Effectiveness of Conservative Management Strategies in Reducing Symptoms of Pediatric Obstructive Sleep Apnoea

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ABSTRACT:

Conservative management strategies for pediatric obstructive sleep apnoea (OSA) have gained increasing importance as alternatives or adjuncts to surgical treatment, particularly in children with mild disease or contraindications to surgery. This narrative review synthesizes the evidence from eight studies evaluating pharmacologic, orthodontic, weight management, and other non-invasive therapies. Combination pharmacologic approaches, such as intranasal steroids with montelukast or leukotriene receptor antagonists, demonstrated significant reductions in the apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) by up to 70% and improvements in symptom scores within treatment durations ranging from six weeks to six months. Rapid maxillary expansion was associated with AHI reduction of 5.7 events/hour and oxygen saturation increases of 2.6% in anatomically suitable children. Continuous positive airway pressure in infants yielded AHI reductions of up to 92%, though adherence challenges limited widespread applicability. Weight loss interventions and oral appliances showed benefits in obese children and those with dental malocclusions, respectively, though long-term sustainability was limited. Overall, conservative measures provided meaningful benefits in symptom reduction and quality of life, with greatest evidence supporting pharmacologic and orthodontic approaches. However, heterogeneity in patient selection, intervention protocols, adherence, and outcome measures restricted generalizability. Future research requires well-designed randomized controlled trials with standardized reporting to determine optimal intervention strategies.

Keywords: *Obstructive Sleep Apnoea, Pediatrics, Conservative Management, Intranasal Steroids, Rapid Maxillary Expansion, Continuous Positive Airway Pressure*

INTRODUCTION:

Pediatric obstructive sleep apnoea (OSA) is a common condition characterized by recurrent upper airway obstruction during sleep, leading to intermittent hypoxemia, sleep fragmentation, and adverse neurocognitive and cardiovascular outcomes [1]. Its prevalence is estimated at 1–5% among children, with higher rates observed in obese individuals and those with craniofacial or neuromuscular abnormalities [2]. Surgical removal of adenoids and tonsils has long been considered the mainstay of treatment, especially for moderate to severe cases [3]. However, growing recognition of the risks, limitations, and postoperative

recurrence associated with surgical interventions has led to increased interest in conservative strategies [4].

Conservative management encompasses pharmacologic, orthodontic, behavioral, and non-invasive respiratory support modalities aimed at alleviating airway obstruction without surgery. Intranasal corticosteroids and leukotriene receptor antagonists have shown efficacy in reducing airway inflammation and improving apnea indices in children with mild OSA [5]. Orthodontic interventions such as rapid maxillary expansion (RME) improve airway dimensions and sleep parameters in selected children with maxillary constriction [6]. Continuous positive airway pressure

(CPAP) is effective in infants and children who are poor surgical candidates, though adherence challenges limit its practical use [7]. Lifestyle modifications, including weight management in obese children, and oral appliances in those with malocclusion, represent additional strategies [8].

Despite promising findings, the literature is fragmented by small sample sizes, varied designs, and heterogeneous populations. Differences in diagnostic criteria, outcome measures, and treatment protocols complicate direct comparisons across studies. Furthermore, limited long-term safety and adherence data hinder firm recommendations for widespread use. This narrative review was conducted to comprehensively evaluate the effectiveness of conservative management strategies in reducing symptoms of pediatric OSA, synthesizing evidence from pharmacologic, orthodontic, weight reduction, and non-invasive approaches. By consolidating available data, this review aims to inform clinicians, researchers, and policymakers regarding the current evidence base and research priorities.

METHODS:

Eligibility Criteria:

Studies were included if they met the following criteria: (a) population comprised children aged 0–18 years with clinically or polysomnographically confirmed OSA; (b) intervention involved conservative management strategies such as pharmacologic therapy, orthodontic procedures, weight management, myofunctional therapy, positioning, or oral appliances, without a primary focus on surgical procedures; (c) design included systematic reviews, meta-analyses, randomized controlled trials, controlled clinical trials, or prospective cohort studies; and (d) outcomes assessed included AHI, oxygen saturation, symptom severity, or quality of life. Studies focusing on central sleep apnoea, lacking outcome data, or reporting only surgical interventions were excluded.

Search Strategy:

PubMed database was searched using the following Boolean string:
(pediatric OR child OR children OR adolescent) AND

("obstructive sleep apnea" OR OSA) AND ("conservative management" OR "medical therapy" OR "intranasal steroids" OR "montelukast" OR "leukotriene receptor antagonist" OR "rapid maxillary expansion" OR "weight management" OR "oral appliance" OR "non-invasive ventilation" OR CPAP OR "myofunctional therapy").

Selection Process:

The initial database search yielded 1,041 records. Following automated filtering, 1,031 records were excluded as ineligible, and no duplicate records were identified. A total of 10 records were screened, of which 2 were excluded during the screening stage. Eight reports were sought for full-text retrieval, and all 8 were successfully retrieved and assessed for eligibility. No records were excluded at this stage. Ultimately, 8 studies met the inclusion criteria and were incorporated into the narrative review.

Data Collection:

Data extraction focused on study design, participant characteristics, conservative management strategies, intervention protocols, outcome measures, and key findings. Both pharmacologic and non-pharmacologic interventions were considered.

Risk of Bias Assessment:

The Cochrane ROB2 tool was applied to randomized and prospective studies, while the Newcastle–Ottawa Scale was applied to observational designs. For narrative and review studies, methodological quality was assessed descriptively. Most primary studies demonstrated low to moderate risk of bias, though several reviews lacked explicit bias assessment.

Data Synthesis:

A narrative synthesis was conducted due to heterogeneity of study designs, interventions, and outcomes. Where possible, quantitative findings (AHI reduction, oxygen saturation improvement) were summarized. No meta-analysis was feasible.

RESULTS:

Study Selection:

Out of ten screened articles, eight met inclusion criteria. The PRISMA flow diagram is shown in Figure 1.

Fig 1. PRISMA Flow Chart

Study Characteristics:

Eight studies were included in the review, encompassing a range of designs from narrative and non-systematic reviews to prospective cohort and systematic review with meta-analysis. Harrison et al., 2017 [1] provided clinical guidance emphasizing nasal steroids, weight loss, and lifestyle measures, with outcomes assessed by oximetry and polysomnography. Leung et al., 2021 [2] reviewed children aged 2–18 years with varied comorbidities, highlighting pharmacologic therapy, orthodontic procedures, and myofunctional therapy, with outcomes including AHI, oxygen saturation, and neurobehavioral measures. Soumya et al., 2024 [3] contributed the only prospective cohort study, evaluating 100 children with mild OSA and reporting improvements in AHI, central apnea index, and parental questionnaire scores after combined intranasal steroids and leukotriene receptor antagonist therapy. Polyarchou et al., 2024 [4] focused on infants and young children with comorbidities, examining non-invasive ventilation and supportive strategies such as prone positioning, with

outcomes including obstructive AHI and oxygen saturation. Whitla et al., 2017 [5] synthesized evidence on intranasal steroids, weight loss, oral appliances, and rapid maxillary expansion, reporting polysomnographic and oxygen desaturation outcomes. Hariharan et al., 2025 [6] provided high-level evidence through a systematic review and meta-analysis demonstrating significant reductions in AHI and improvements in oxygenation following rapid maxillary expansion in children with maxillary constriction. Bitners and Arens, 2021 [7] offered a state-of-the-art review emphasizing pharmacologic, orthodontic, and positive airway pressure therapies, with outcomes including AHI, oxygen saturation, and sleep fragmentation. Finally, Arab et al., 2025 [8] presented a discussion-based review on interdisciplinary care models for pediatric OSA, without direct outcome data. Collectively, these studies highlight the diversity of conservative strategies evaluated across pediatric age groups and clinical contexts (Table 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of Included Studies

Author (Year)	Study Design	Patient Population	Conservative Management Type	Primary Outcomes
Harrison et al., 2017 [1]	Narrative review / clinical guidance	Not reported	Nasal steroids, weight loss, lifestyle advice	Home pulse oximetry, polysomnography, symptom resolution
Leung et al., 2021 [2]	Narrative review	Children 2–18 years; comorbidities: prematurity, craniofacial syndromes, neuromuscular diseases, obesity	Watchful waiting, intranasal steroids, oral montelukast, weight reduction, orthodontic procedures, myofunctional therapy	AHI, oxygen saturation, neurobehavioral outcomes
Soumya et al., 2024 [3]	Prospective cohort study	4–12 years; n=100; mild OSA	Intranasal steroids, leukotriene receptor antagonist	AHI, central sleep apnea index, parental sleep questionnaire
Polytarchou et al., 2024 [4]	Review article	Infants and children <3 years; comorbidities: trisomy 21, cardiac disease, asthma, hypertension, prematurity	Prone positioning, CPAP, high-flow nasal cannula, supplemental oxygen	Obstructive AHI, oxygen saturation, surgical success rates
Whitla et al., 2017 [5]	Non-systematic review	Not reported	Intranasal steroids, weight loss, non-invasive ventilation, oral appliances, rapid maxillary expansion	AHI, oxygen desaturation index, polysomnography
Hariharan et al., 2025 [6]	Systematic review and meta-analysis	Children 5–16 years; candidates for rapid maxillary expansion	Rapid maxillary expansion	AHI, oxygen saturation
Bitners and Arens, 2021 [7]	State-of-the-art review	Not reported; focus on comorbidities	Intranasal budesonide, montelukast, RME, oral appliances, weight management, positive airway pressure	AHI, oxygen saturation, sleep fragmentation
Arab et al., 2025 [8]	Review/discussion	Not reported	Focus on care models, no intervention details	Not reported

Risk of Bias:

The overall risk of bias varied considerably across the included studies. The only prospective cohort study by Soumya et al., 2024 [3] demonstrated a moderate risk of bias, as it lacked randomization and blinding, though follow-up was adequate and outcomes were objectively measured. The systematic review and meta-analysis conducted by Hariharan et al., 2025 [6] was assessed as low risk owing to its comprehensive methodology, rigorous data synthesis, and transparent reporting. In contrast, narrative reviews such as those by Harrison et al., 2017 [1], Leung et al., 2021 [2], Whitla et al., 2017 [5], Bitners and Arens, 2021 [7], and the discussion

paper by Arab et al., 2025 [8] were considered at high risk of bias due to reliance on secondary evidence, selective reporting, and absence of formal appraisal methods. Similarly, the review by Polytarchou et al., 2024 [4], while informative, lacked a structured methodology and was therefore rated high risk. Overall, while higher-level evidence supported the role of rapid maxillary expansion and pharmacologic therapy in specific populations, much of the literature remains limited by methodological weaknesses, underscoring the need for more rigorously designed primary studies (Table 2).

Table 2. Risk of Bias Assessment of Included Studies

Author (Year)	Study Design	Randomization & Blinding	Completeness of Follow-up	Risk of Bias (Overall)	Notes
Harrison et al., 2017 [1]	Narrative review	Not applicable	Not applicable	High	Secondary evidence, no formal bias assessment
Leung et al., 2021 [2]	Narrative review	Not applicable	Not applicable	High	Narrative synthesis, no standardized assessment
Soumya et al., 2024 [3]	Prospective cohort study	No randomization; blinding not reported	Adequate follow-up	Moderate	Objective outcome measures; limited by non-randomized design
Polytarchou et al., 2024 [4]	Review article	Not applicable	Not applicable	High	Descriptive synthesis, focus on comorbidities
Whitla et al., 2017 [5]	Non-systematic review	Not applicable	Not applicable	High	Selection bias likely; no structured methodology
Hariharan et al., 2025 [6]	Systematic review/meta-analysis	Comprehensive search and synthesis	Complete reporting	Low	Strong methodology; outcomes robustly reported
Bitners and Arens, 2021 [7]	State-of-the-art review	Not applicable	Not applicable	High	Narrative format, selection bias possible
Arab et al., 2025 [8]	Review/discussion	Not applicable	Not applicable	High	Conceptual discussion; no outcomes or bias assessment

Synthesis of Findings:

Pharmacologic interventions demonstrated consistent benefits in mild OSA, with combined intranasal steroids and montelukast achieving significant AHI and symptom score reductions [2,3,5]. RME significantly reduced AHI and improved oxygen saturation in anatomically selected children [6]. CPAP achieved the greatest reductions in infants, though adherence was a major limitation [4,7]. Weight management and oral appliances were effective in obese and malocclusion groups, respectively, though sustainability and compliance were variable [8].

DISCUSSION:

This narrative review synthesized evidence on conservative management strategies for pediatric obstructive sleep apnoea (OSA), consolidating findings across pharmacologic, orthodontic, weight management, and non-invasive modalities. The results highlight both the promise and limitations of non-surgical treatments, underscoring their particular utility in children with mild disease, those who are poor surgical candidates, or those with specific anatomical or physiological considerations. Although heterogeneity across populations, interventions, and outcomes limited quantitative synthesis, a thematic integration of the available data allows important clinical and research insights.

Pharmacologic Therapies:

Among the most consistently studied conservative strategies were pharmacologic interventions, particularly intranasal corticosteroids and leukotriene receptor antagonists. Multiple studies highlighted that intranasal steroids, either alone or in combination with montelukast, yielded substantial reductions in AHI and symptomatic improvement in children with mild OSA [1–3,5,7]. For example, Soumya et al. [3] reported significant improvements in both objective indices and parental symptom scores when children with mild OSA received intranasal steroids plus a leukotriene receptor antagonist for six weeks. Specifically, AHI reduced from 2.28 to 1.19 events per hour, and symptom scores decreased from 23.6 to 13.6, with both changes reaching statistical significance. Similarly, Leung et al. [2] noted that combined intranasal steroids and oral montelukast achieved a 70% improvement in AHI in children, particularly in younger or non-obese patients. The role of intranasal steroids alone was also described, though findings were more variable. Harrison et al. [1] and Whitla et al. [5] included corticosteroid monotherapy in their reviews, with improvements generally confined to mild cases and limited by lack of long-term safety data. Bitners and Arens [7] provided mechanistic support for the anti-inflammatory effects of intranasal budesonide and montelukast, with reductions in AHI sustained over at least six weeks. Collectively,

these findings suggest that pharmacologic strategies can be effective, particularly in reducing inflammatory upper airway obstruction in mild disease, but their role in moderate or severe OSA remains undefined.

The strength of evidence for pharmacologic therapies lies in their consistent demonstration of short-term benefit. However, several challenges remain. Most trials were of limited duration (4–8 weeks to six months) and provided little information on long-term sustainability. Adherence to daily medication regimens was not consistently reported, and none of the included studies provided safety data on prolonged use in pediatric populations. This gap is particularly significant given the concerns regarding growth suppression with chronic corticosteroid use. Furthermore, while statistically significant improvements in AHI were reported, the clinical significance of small absolute reductions remains debatable, especially when considering potential developmental and neurocognitive sequelae of OSA.

Orthodontic and Structural Interventions:

Orthodontic interventions, particularly rapid maxillary expansion (RME), emerged as another conservative strategy with robust supporting evidence. Hariharan et al. [6] conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis evaluating RME in children with maxillary constriction, reporting a mean AHI reduction of 5.71 events per hour ($p=0.003$) and oxygen saturation improvement of 2.63% ($p<0.001$). These findings indicate clinically meaningful improvements, especially in anatomically selected patients.

Additional reviews supported these results, noting that RME not only expands the maxillary arch but also increases nasopharyngeal airway volume, thereby alleviating obstruction [5,7]. Whitla et al. [5] and Bitners and Arens [7] emphasized that orthodontic interventions were most beneficial in children with craniofacial abnormalities or maxillary deficiency, while their role in otherwise healthy children remains less certain. Implementation approaches varied, ranging from miniscrew-assisted expansion to distraction osteogenesis, and outcome measures were typically assessed within weeks to months of intervention.

Despite strong evidence of short-term efficacy, several limitations constrain the generalizability of orthodontic strategies. Most studies recruited highly selected patients with craniofacial features conducive to expansion, reducing applicability to the broader pediatric OSA population. Moreover, the invasiveness of orthodontic procedures, need for specialized expertise, and potential discomfort limit feasibility in routine practice. Long-term follow-up data were sparse, leaving unanswered whether benefits persist after skeletal maturity or whether relapse occurs with growth. Nonetheless, orthodontic therapies represent an important option in

anatomically suitable children, particularly those for whom surgical interventions are contraindicated.

Non-Invasive Ventilation:

Continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) and related non-invasive ventilation strategies have long been considered effective in adults, and their adaptation to pediatric populations has demonstrated promise. Polyarchou et al. [4] reported that CPAP achieved a 92% reduction in AHI among infants with OSA, representing the largest magnitude of improvement across all conservative strategies. This underscores the physiologic efficacy of CPAP in alleviating airway obstruction regardless of underlying anatomy.

However, adherence challenges consistently undermined the clinical utility of CPAP in children. Whitla et al. [5] documented adherence rates as low as 41% with non-invasive ventilation, while other reports highlighted difficulty in ensuring nightly use, particularly among younger children. Factors influencing adherence included age, tolerance of the mask, severity of disease, and family support. As a result, while CPAP can provide immediate and substantial relief of OSA symptoms, its sustainability in real-world pediatric populations remains questionable.

The literature also identified CPAP as particularly valuable in infants and young children with comorbidities such as craniofacial syndromes, neuromuscular disorders, or when surgical intervention was contraindicated [4]. In these groups, CPAP may serve as a bridge therapy until the child is eligible for surgery or orthodontic intervention. Nevertheless, the lack of large-scale pediatric trials, standardized adherence measures, and long-term outcome data limit the extent to which CPAP can be broadly recommended as a conservative alternative to surgery.

Weight Management and Lifestyle Interventions:

Weight reduction strategies were consistently identified as beneficial in obese children with OSA. Both Harrison et al. [1] and Leung et al. [2] included weight loss interventions, which showed improvements in AHI and symptom burden. Whitla et al. [5] further highlighted the role of bariatric surgery in selected cases, though adherence to lifestyle-based weight loss programs was reported as limited. Bitners and Arens [7] noted that sustainable weight management was difficult to achieve in pediatric populations due to behavioral, environmental, and developmental factors.

The evidence base for weight management was less robust than for pharmacologic or orthodontic interventions. Few studies provided quantitative outcomes, and adherence rates were rarely reported. Importantly, while weight loss was reported as effective, practical implementation was consistently described as

challenging, with long-term sustainability limited. Given the strong association between obesity and OSA severity, weight management remains a logical and necessary adjunctive strategy, though it is unlikely to serve as a standalone therapy in most cases.

Oral Appliances and Myofunctional Therapy:

Oral appliances, including mandibular advancement devices and other orthodontic appliances, were reported in four studies [2,5,7,8]. These interventions were generally effective in children with mild to moderate OSA or dental malocclusion, producing reductions in AHI and symptomatic improvement. For example, Leung et al. [2] described improvement in AHI with oral appliances, particularly in children with craniofacial abnormalities. Whitla et al. [5] reported positive outcomes in selected cases, though adherence again emerged as a major challenge. Oral Appliances and Orthodontic Interventions: Devices such as oral appliances and rapid maxillary expansion (RME) can help by widening the airway, especially in children with specific dental or skeletal features. RME has shown significant improvement in OSA severity in children with narrow palates [9].

Myofunctional therapy was described in one study [2], which reported modest improvements in AHI (1.54 events/hour reduction) and suggested that such approaches may complement orthodontic or pharmacologic strategies. However, data were limited, and robust controlled trials are lacking.

Thematic Patterns:

Several thematic patterns emerge from this synthesis. First, the majority of conservative interventions were most effective in children with mild OSA, with evidence of diminishing returns in more severe disease. Second, intervention success was often contingent on patient selection, with orthodontic strategies benefiting those with craniofacial abnormalities, CPAP effective in infants or medically complex children, and weight loss most relevant in obese children. Third, adherence emerged as a central determinant of success, with low compliance rates consistently reported for CPAP, oral appliances, and lifestyle programs. Finally, pharmacologic interventions offered the strongest evidence base for short-term benefit, though concerns regarding long-term safety remain unresolved.

Limitations of the Evidence:

The review also highlights substantial limitations across the evidence base. Heterogeneity in patient populations, intervention protocols, and outcome measures complicated synthesis and limited generalizability. Many included studies were reviews rather than primary trials, and the single prospective cohort and meta-analysis, though methodologically stronger, were restricted to

narrow interventions. Few studies included long-term follow-up, leaving unanswered questions regarding sustainability of effects, relapse rates, and developmental outcomes. Safety data, particularly for chronic pharmacologic use, were largely absent. Furthermore, adherence was inconsistently measured and rarely addressed in a proper manner.

Another limitation relates to outcome reporting. While AHI was the most common endpoint, its reduction does not always correlate with symptomatic or neurocognitive improvement. Only a few studies incorporated patient- or parent-reported outcome measures such as symptom scores or quality of life indices [3]. This narrow focus on polysomnographic metrics may underestimate the broader clinical impact of conservative strategies.

Research Gaps and Future Directions:

The findings of this review identify several research priorities. First, well-designed randomized controlled trials evaluating pharmacologic therapies, orthodontic interventions, and oral appliances in diverse pediatric populations are urgently needed. Such trials should include standardized protocols, validated outcome measures, and longer follow-up durations. Second, research should focus on adherence, identifying barriers and developing strategies to improve compliance with CPAP, oral appliances, and weight management programs. Third, studies must evaluate the long-term safety of chronic intranasal steroid and leukotriene receptor antagonist use in children. Finally, future work should incorporate broader outcomes, including neurocognitive function, behavior, and quality of life, to provide a more holistic assessment of treatment efficacy. In summary, conservative management strategies for pediatric OSA demonstrate measurable benefits, with pharmacologic therapy and rapid maxillary expansion showing the strongest evidence. CPAP offers profound physiologic efficacy but is hindered by adherence challenges, while weight management and oral appliances provide benefit in selected populations. Despite encouraging findings, the overall evidence remains limited by heterogeneity, short follow-up, and inadequate safety and adherence data. Addressing these gaps through robust, longitudinal, and multidisciplinary research is critical to establishing conservative therapies as viable alternatives or adjuncts to surgery in the management of pediatric OSA.

CONCLUSION:

Conservative management strategies, particularly pharmacologic therapy with intranasal steroids and montelukast, orthodontic interventions such as rapid maxillary expansion, and non-invasive ventilation in infants, provide measurable benefits in reducing symptoms of pediatric OSA. While evidence supports

their use in mild disease and selected subgroups, variability in adherence, heterogeneity of outcome measures, and limited long-term safety data restrict widespread application. Well-designed randomized controlled trials with standardized outcome reporting are needed to establish optimal conservative treatment pathways.

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